

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Factors affecting consumers buying decision behavior via online media

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Abstract

At present, the electronic commerce business (e-commerce) has grown steadily due to advanced technology. Consumers can access the internet conveniently and quickly, right at their fingertips. Entrepreneurs in various businesses also see that, at this time, e-commerce is the main sales channel to reach consumers. Especially doing e-commerce through applications because of the ease of use. It has a variety of payment systems, including a product management system and delivery to the destination with payment, which facilitates consumers' convenience and gives them more confidence in the system of ordering products through online applications. The purpose of this research is to study the personal factors of consumers buying fashion clothes via Instagram, personal factors related to consumer behaviour, and online promotion strategies related to consumer behaviour. Including factors in the marketing mix and factors in technology acceptance, namely product factors, price distribution channels, marketing promotion, and technology acceptance security, reliability, and personalised service. That affects the decision to buy products via Instagram for the benefit of selling products online.

Keywords: Electronic commerce; Consumer behaviours; Technology; Logistics network; Online application

1. Introduction

Nowadays, technology is growing rapidly. network technology Computers have evolved in many forms Computer networks that cover areas and numbers The most active is the computer network known as the Internet. The Internet is a communication innovation that is rapidly growing and gaining popularity. because it makes the person convenient, fast, and economical. in the news centre endlessly, resulting in change requests for information in various fields such as economy, politics, culture, morality, education, transportation, communication, military, etc., including in the field of online business. information gathered together in a large number, and the Internet has plenty of information to choose from. To meet the needs The work of all groups, genders, walks of life, and professions is a tool that combines many qualities and characteristics with the key features and characteristics of the Internet. service requests news and information in various formats quickly and up-to-date, and the Internet is still useful for people to study and quickly grab information as needed.

When the widespread expansion of the Internet results in the rate of Internet use in developing countries having the opportunity to expand higher, which may cause the purchase of goods online to increase, today's businesses pay attention to the use of applications as a tool to sell products and services to consumers. Because it is a technology that enables businesses to operate efficiently, organisations that conduct business in the form of electronic commerce will make consumers quickly get the information they need and can purchase products and services through the application anytime, anywhere. and it is extremely important to make adjustments. Product sales channels to change product presentation channels and communicate with new customers. Buyers and sellers can use it easily. easier and more convenient whether the system keeps safe in Payment can check the order through the internet. Today, this general product has become known as a market on the Internet network.

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2. Review of Literature

The scholar Michal AUGUSTINI (2014) did a study on the role of social media and content marketing as a part of an effective online marketing strategy. The objectives of the research are customer retention and satisfaction; companies are using social media for a direct dialog with customers to provide them support; on the other hand, content marketing is more focused on demand generation. Quality content on websites can build a relationship with potential clients and nurture them towards a lead conversion or purchase.

Michal AUGUSTINI has used descriptive and analytical research methodology that is purely based on primary data. Primary data were collected through a questionnaire. Descriptive statistics like mean, standard deviation, and analysis and measurement of the

efforts are essential to direct social business, and so is the content marketing strategy. Numbers will always show if the strategies are working or not. In order to measure the success of a content marketing strategy, goals have to be defined. And these have to be in accordance with the social business goals and overall vision. The analysis showed that companies had improved the level of service they could provide to their customers with e-commerce. They found out that many of these practices are often unconsciously adhered to, and applying others to build a whole concept will help companies become successful in the online marketing area. This thesis gave me a deeper understanding of social media and content marketing that I have immediately applied in practice. I don't have solid results now to prove that all the steps done in VideoFlot will guarantee their success, but nonetheless, it is a good starting point to apply all the knowledge from the thesis and help VideoFlot become an effective social business.

Matthews, Hendrickson, and Denise (2016) did a research paper on Environmental and Economic Effects of E-Commerce: A Case Study of Book Publishing and Retail Logistics.

One of the major objectives of this research was to analyse the different logistics networks and assess the environmental and cost effects of different delivery systems. Matthews and other scholars have used qualitative research methods.

The research paper is entirely case study based which includes various tables that explain comparative estimate costs of Logistics and Returns for Traditional Versus E-Commerce Book Retailing and comparison between other elements of e-commerce.

They found out that by altering these critical parameters such as shipping distances, return rates, and shopping allocations, e-commerce was shown to be somewhat more costly than the traditional system. Nevertheless, the base analysis case suggests that e-commerce sales have a cost advantage and environmental benefits.

The scholars, **Dr Dave Chaffey and Danyl Bosomworth (2013)** did a study on the role of Digital marketing strategy Planning Template. The objectives of the research suggest hierarchy of measures may help in larger organisations and Align goals to the business and marketing goals and how substantiate them using the approach described in our improving results from digital marketing ebook. This example shows how one Expert member used the “menu” of KPIs in Ebook to select the most relevant measures for them to put into their reporting.

Dr. Dave Chaffey and Danyl Bosomworth have used descriptive and analytical research methodologies that are purely based on primary data. Primary data was collected through a questionnaire and analysed using the power of analytics to test, learn, and refine. The analysis showed the power of analytics to review and improve campaigns, social media marketing, and site(s), but it's difficult to know where to start beyond browsing charts of trends in visits. Guides, templates, and online training on Google Analytics will give you a structure to mine more from analytics. They found out that you should define a plan to develop the most relevant content to grow your audience through sharing (amplification) and increase brand appeal. The content marketing matrix is a great way to review the current use of content marketing and identify new types of content.

The scholars, **Meng-jie Liao a b, Jian Zhang a, Rui-mei Wang and Lin Qi a (2021)** did a study on the role of Simulation research on online marketing strategies of branded agricultural products based on the difference in opinion leader attitudes. The objectives of the research on how to optimise online marketing strategies based on the difference in opinion leaders' attitudes remains a problem demanding prompt solutions for agricultural product brand enterprises.

Meng-jie Liao a b, Jian Zhang a, Rui-mei Wang, and Lin Qi a have used descriptive and analytical research methodology to analyse the choice mechanism of agricultural product brand enterprises for online promotion strategies on the premise of opinion leaders' stand differentiation under evolutionary game perspective and simulation and analysis. In

accordance with evolutionary game theory, individuals with limited rationality lack the ability to compute personal payoff earnings and make the best decisions, and they can only make the best decisions through constant trials and learning. The analysis showed that the fine was defined as the fine imposed by agricultural product brand enterprises on opinion leaders for negative brand promotion. T is defined as the opportunity cost missed by agricultural product brand companies because they do not invest in positive brand promotion. They found out that On the premise of preference differences between online opinion leaders, the research assumes that opinion leaders hold different motivations and attitudes toward agricultural product brand promotion. Subsequently, it combines with evolutionary game theory to construct a game model for online marketing strategies of branded agricultural products, examines brand enterprises' brand promotion advantage strategies for different opinion leaders, and consults dynamic visualisation simulation to verify model validity. Additionally, throughout the multi-subject simulation experiment, the research further investigates the influence of varying punishment intensity on opinion leaders' negative marketing.

Sameer Kumar and Palo Petersen (2006) did a study on the impact of e-commerce on lowering operational costs and raising customer satisfaction. The objective of the research is to understand how e-commerce has affected companies' abilities to serve customers' needs and raise their level of satisfaction.

Sameer Kumar and Palo Petersen's exploratory data analysis and logistics regression were used to analyse data collected from a multi-industry company survey. The Analysis showed that companies have been able to improve the level of service they can provide to their customers with e-commerce. They found out that the originality value of the study is unique in terms of applying a logistics regression approach to multi-company data across various industries to analyse the impact of e-commerce on the service aspect of business operations. It also addresses the research question of whether e-commerce use in a business effectively raises the level of customer service and overall business operation to a more desirable quality. The research showed that there is a direct correlation between the use of e-commerce and improved customer service. In particular, e-commerce has improved the availability of information, reduced processing errors, reduced response times, lowered the cost of services, and effectively raised customer satisfaction and the level of service that customers expect to receive.

2.1. Statement of the problem

The e-commerce business has developed greatly. Due to changing consumer behaviour Purchasing more products and services via the Internet, including entering the e-commerce market for businesses, As a result, the Internet has developed more capabilities. Creates a lot of consumer confidence. Consumers are entering an era where online media has an influence on the behaviour of purchasing goods and services, especially mobile phones, which have become tools to help customers buy products, such as finding information about goods and stores before buying and comparing prices. Read the reviews of other customers. Even taking pictures of products on online media. Because nowadays there are many online businesses. and is highly competitive, making the researchers interested in It will study the behaviour of customers in buying goods and services online as a guideline for formulating marketing strategies for online businesses in order to meet the needs of customers as much as possible.

Need of the study

The relevance of this study is as follows:

- The majority of the study is on consumer online shopping behaviour.
- This study will increase our understanding of online consumption.

Objective of the research

- To study consumers' online shopping behaviour.
- To study demographic factors that affect behaviour in purchasing products through the media online consumer
- To study marketing factors that affect consumers' online shopping behaviour

3. Research Methodology

The study is descriptive and conceptual, based on secondary data. It aims at studying the factors affecting consumers' buying behaviour via online media. Major sources of secondary data are journals, articles, and a few thesis papers.

3.1. Conceptual Explanation

Consumer behaviour refers to individual expressions that are directly related to consumer behaviour. Use online products including the decision-making process that affects the expression, number of purchases of each product of the consumer.

Social media facilitates content sharing, collaborations, and interactions. These social media platforms and applications exist in various forms such as social bookmarking, rating, video, pictures, podcasts, wikis, microblogging, social blogs, and weblogs. Social networkers, governmental organisations, and business firms are using social media to communicate, with its use increasing tremendously (Cheung et al., 2021). Governmental organisations and business firms use social media for marketing and advertising. Integrated marketing activities can be performed with less cost and effort due to the seamless interactions and communication among consumer partners, events, media, digital services, and retailers *via* social media (Tafesse and Wien, 2018).

3.2. Discuss

Electronic commerce and digital technology today Make the sales model and strategy Today's market changes, especially the growing rate of electronic commerce (e-commerce) worldwide, are attracting more attention from investors, companies, and consumers as well. E-commerce has changed the economy and the way we do business. This has forced companies to find new ways to expand their markets. By adjusting products and services to meet the needs of customers as much as possible, including the process of delivering products and services to be more efficient as an e-service. Rust and Kannan (2002) have said that the factors leading to the success of the company depend on harnessing the Internet to become a better service marketing tool that can promote and increase good relationships with consumers. Therefore, the company must be aware of the customer's point of view and create satisfaction. to customers the most.

Figure 1 Time spent on Media

The survey found that, at an average of 2 hours and 27 minutes per day, social media accounted for the largest single share of our connected media time, at 35 percent of the total. Our time on social media has increased again over the past year as well, increasing by 2 minutes per day (+1.4 percent).

However, social media's total internet timeshare has decreased slightly since the start of the COVID-19 pandemic. Mainly because people are open to new online activities. We've had a lot going on in the past two years, so it's quite fitting. Social media therefore has a smaller share of total online time than people spend doing other things. less online.

Figure 2 Total online time

4. Results

Table 1 Demographic Profile of Particulars

Particulars	Demographic Profile	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	13	43.3
	Female	17	56.7
Occupation	Student	23	93.3
	Business	1	3.3
	Service	0	0
	Other	1	3.3

As per the table 1 when we analyse the demographic profile of people, majority is female (56.7%) and students (93.3%). As per table male is 43.3%, AS per occupation only 3.3% people doing business and other professions.

Table 2 Response to aware of online shopping concepts

Response to aware of online shopping concepts	
Yes	- 100%
No	-0

As per Table 2 everyone agree that they are aware of online shopping concepts

Table 3 Response to What prompts you to shopping for the desired product from social media

Response to What prompts you to shopping for the desired product from social media	
Brand	- 53.3%
Quality	-40%
Price	-6.7%
Service	-0%

As per table 3 majority of people go with brand (53.3%) , 40% and 6.7% respondents respectively go with quality and price

Table 4 Response to How often do you purchase online

Response to How often do you purchase online	
Very Often	- 23.3%
Often	- 23.3%
Some Times	- 53.3%
Rariley	- 0%
Never	- 0%

As per table 4 majority of the respondents do online purchase some times (53.3%), And 23.3% respondents purchase Very often and often respectively.

Table 5 Response to online shopping

Objective	Response 1	Response 2	Response 3	Response 4	Response 5
Motivation for online shopping	At leisure 0%	During offers/promotions 43.3%	On need 56.7%	Mood / Desire 0%	Regularly 0%
Delivery of the product is done usually	At office 0%	At home 100%	Through friend 0%	Collect from courier office 0%	
Make the payment during internet shopping	Credit card 13.3%	Cash on delivery 0%	Internet banking 86.7%	eWallet 0%	
Faced the problem of shopping online	Yes 10%	No 90%			
Buy more often from social media	Fashion Accessories 6.7%	Sports 0%	Computer and Accessories 3.3%	Mobile and Accessories 10%	
Feel that online shopping makes comparison easy	Strong disagree 0%	Disagree 0%	Natural 43.3%	Agree 53.3%	Strong agree 3.3%
Online shopping is risky	Strong disagree 0%	Disagree 36.7%	Natural 53.3%	Agree 10%	Strong agree 0%

As per the table 56.7% respondents do online shopping because of need and 43.3% because of offers and promotions. 100% respondents deliver their product at home.86.7% of respondents make payment through internet banking and 13.3% use credit card. Only 10% face problems during shopping and 90% don't face any. Majority of the people buy

fashion accessories (86.7%), 3.3% buy computer accessories and 10% buy mobile accessories. 53.3% respondents agree that online shopping makes comparison easy, 3.3% strongly agree and 43.36 go with neutral. Only 10% agree that online shopping is risky, 53.3% disagree that online shopping is risky and 53.3% choose a neutral option.

5. Conclusion and Suggestion

Factors affecting consumers' buying decision-making behaviour via online media The key factor comes from the fact that businesses nowadays view e-commerce as an important sales channel. access to consumers as well as the entry of service providers from abroad As a result, there is competition in providing services to meet the needs of consumers as much as possible. highly regarded both in terms of security and reliability. Or having a product management system and transporting it to the destination with payment (warehouse and fulfilment). In addition, smartphones are still cheap. It is another factor that allows almost everyone to access the Internet. 24/7 online shopping service from home, office, or anywhere that has internet access because it can save energy. It's time to go out and buy products. By yourself at various stores is still a good choice for people. Nowadays, shopping through online channels is more reliable and efficient than before, for example, in the event of a product malfunction. Damaged, damaged, or mis-delivered. Many companies already have a policy to deal with these problems with refunds or returns. Including having an inspection system for payment and delivery situations as well.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

References

- [1] www.hootsuite.com (Figure-1&2)
- [2] www.wikipedia.org
- [3] <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2214317320302304>
- [4] <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/17410380610648263/full/html>
- [5] <https://images.template.net/wp-content/uploads/2016/06/27115818/Digital-Marketing-Strategy-Template.pdf>
- [6] <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.3141/1763-02>
- [7] https://www.academia.edu/7070532/Social_media_and_content_marketing_as_a_part_of_an_effective_online_marketing_strategy
- [8] Goel, M. R., & Diwan, M. M. (2022). Influence of Social Media Marketing on Buying Decision Making Process of Consumers. *Mathematical Statistician and Engineering Applications*.
- [9] Fachmi, M., Setiawan, I. P., & Hidayat, A. (2019). Analysis of factors affecting consumer purchase decision at online shops.
- [10] Ertemel, A. V., & Ammoura, A. (2016). The role of social media advertising in consumer buying behavior. *International Journal of Commerce and Finance*.
- [11] Ertemel, A. V., & Ammoura, A. (2016). The role of social media advertising in consumer buying behavior. *International Journal of Commerce and Finance*.
- [12] Hanaysha, J. R. (2022). Impact of social media marketing features on consumer's purchase decision in the fast-food industry: Brand trust as a mediator. *International Journal of Information Management Data Insights*.